

Hydrogen sulfide signaling in plant adaptations to adverse conditions: molecular mechanisms

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Highlights: This review focuses on recent advances relating to H₂S signaling mechanisms. Interconnections between H₂S and H₂O₂ at the posttranslational modification level and with ABA in stomatal movement are highlighted.

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Abstract

Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is a signaling molecule that regulates critical processes and allows plants to adapt to adverse conditions. The molecular mechanism underlying the H₂S action relies on its chemical reactivity, and the mainly characterized is the persulfidation, which involves the modification of protein thiol groups, resulting in the formation of persulfide groups. This modification derives a change of protein function, altering catalytic activity or intracellular location and inducing important physiological effects. H₂S cannot react directly with thiols but instead can react with oxidized cysteine residues; therefore, H₂O₂ signaling through sulfenylation is required for persulfidation. A comparative study performed in this review reveals 82% of identity between the sulfenylome and persulfidome. With regard to abscisic acid (ABA) signaling, widespread evidence shows an interconnection between H₂S and ABA in the plant response to environmental stress. Proteomic analyses have revealed persulfidation of several proteins involved in the ABA signaling network and have shown that persulfidation is triggered in response to ABA. In guard cells, a complex interaction of H₂S and ABA signaling has also been described, and the persulfidation of specific signaling components seems to be the underlying mechanism.

Keywords: Abscisic acid, persulfidation, proteomics, redox modifications, stomatal movement, sulfenylation

Abbreviations: ABA, abscisic acid; CO, carbon monoxide; H₂O₂, hydrogen sulfide; NO, nitric oxide; PEG, polyethylene glycol; ROS, reactive oxygen species; -SOH, sulfenic; -SO₂H, sulfinic; -SO₃H, sulfonic

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Introduction

Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is a colorless gas with a characteristic unpleasant odor. In nature, H₂S is present in volcanic gas, hot springs, rock salts, and natural gas, as well as in emissions produced as a result of industrial activity. In biological systems, H₂S can be considered an ancient molecule since it originates from bacterial anaerobic metabolism. In the absence of oxygen, sulfur-reducing microorganisms use different forms of oxidized sulfur as electron acceptors during the degradation of simple organic matter, producing H₂S and CO₂ (Offre *et al.*, 2013). H₂S is additionally used by sulfur-oxidizing bacteria as an electron donor in anoxygenic photosynthesis to produce oxidized sulfur compounds (Johnston *et al.*, 2009).

Hydrogen sulfide has long been considered a toxic molecule dangerous to the environment and complex biological organisms. In mammals, the presence of sulfide in mitochondria causes the inhibition of cytochrome c oxidase of the respiratory chain, as does the presence of carbon monoxide (CO) and nitric oxide (NO) (Cooper and Brown, 2008). However, below a specific concentration threshold, CO, NO and H₂S affect various cellular events and are currently considered to be signaling molecules that function as physiological gasotransmitters (Wang, 2014). In plants, H₂S is also recognized to have the same relevance as other signaling molecules, such as NO and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) (Aroca *et al.*, 2020; Aroca *et al.*, 2018; Calderwood and Kopriva, 2014). All these molecules, including H₂S, show toxicity/signaling duality, depending on the concentration threshold.

Although H₂S is known to be present in mammalian tissues, it was first established in the late 20th century its intracellular production and signaling function as neuromodulator (Abe and Kimura, 1996). H₂S is produced endogenously by cells through different enzymes involved in cysteine metabolism, both in mammals and in plants. In plants, H₂S is also produced in the photosynthetic sulfate assimilation pathway in the chloroplast (Gotor *et al.*, 2019). Intensive research on H₂S has been carried out in recent years both in animals and in plants, and an impressive exponential increase in the number of original publications and reviews has been occurred. Consequently, the number of biological functions in which sulfide is known to be involved has rapidly increased. In plants, H₂S has been shown to be essential in regulating a wide range of vital processes. H₂S improves the tolerance and protection of plants to numerous adverse environmental conditions, and in this way, it allows plant adaptability and viability, and its beneficial effects play a role in important aspects of development (Zhang *et al.*, 2021b; Zhou *et al.*, 2021b). Sulfide also regulates critical processes, including autophagy and abscisic acid (ABA)-dependent stomatal movement (Gotor *et al.*, 2019; Laureano-Marin *et al.*, 2020; Zhang *et al.*, 2020). In addition, the interplay of H₂S with other signaling molecules and phytohormones in multiple physiological processes has been extensively described (Aroca *et al.*, 2020).

Despite the very large number of plant studies that are continuously being conducted, studies on the molecular mechanisms through which sulfide exerts its regulatory effects are still scarce. We believe that this aspect deserves specific attention and this review highlights the progress obtained in understanding the mechanism of action of sulfide in plant systems. The most recent outcomes on the mechanism of the sulfide control of guard cell ABA signaling are also highlighted.

Hydrogen sulfide action

The reaction mechanism in which H₂S participates and exerts regulatory and signaling function is complex, and it is necessary to take into account the complex reactivity of this molecule. Hydrogen sulfide encompasses neutral H₂S and anionic forms (hydrosulfide, HS⁻, and sulfide, S²⁻) with pK_{a1} and pK_{a2} values of 6.9 and >12, respectively (Kabil and Banerjee, 2010). Therefore, in aqueous solution, H₂S exists in equilibrium with its H⁺ and HS⁻ anionic forms, these latter are unable to cross organelle membranes. Under physiological pH conditions, two-thirds of hydrogen sulfide exists in the form of HS⁻. However, the lipid solubility of H₂S and its membrane permeability promote the biological distribution of sulfide species within cells (Cuevasanta *et al.*, 2012).

The mechanism of action of H₂S is related to the characteristics of acid-base behavior and chemical reactivity with other biochemical molecules, such as low-molecular weight thiols, protein thiols, protein metal centers and biological oxidants. Among these oxidants, hydroxyl radical (HO[•]), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂[•]), superoxide radical (O₂^{•-}), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), peroxyntirite (ONOOH) and hypochlorite (HOCl) can support H₂S oxidation (Li and Lancaster, 2013; Zaffagnini *et al.*, 2019).

Metalloproteins are well-established biochemical targets of H₂S that covalently attach to heme porphyrins. Thus, H₂S acts as a potent inhibitor of mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase, inhibiting mitochondrial respiration, releasing cytochrome c during apoptosis and stimulating procaspase 9 persulfidation (Vitvitsky *et al.*, 2018). H₂S can also react quickly and reversibly with other ferric heme proteins such as methemoglobin and leghemoglobin to reduce their iron center and form a complex (Boubeta *et al.*, 2020; Jensen and Fago, 2018). In addition to modifying heme proteins, H₂S can also modify Zn-finger proteins but leads to persulfidation and rapid thiol oxidation (Lange *et al.*, 2019).

A second mechanism of action of H₂S that is well established in mammalian and plant systems is the modification of proteins by the oxidation of cysteine residues to form corresponding persulfides

(Filipovic, 2015; Gotor *et al.*, 2019). Protein thiol persulfidation has been widely described for numerous proteins, and it was initially described as S-sulfhydration in mouse liver. Susceptibility of several proteins to modification by sulfide has been determined (Filipovic *et al.*, 2018; Mustafa *et al.*, 2009). In plants, three high-throughput proteomic analyses also revealed the presence of persulfidation in the Arabidopsis proteome, showing more than 3400 and 5214 proteins susceptible to persulfidation in leaf and root tissue, respectively (Aroca *et al.*, 2017a; Aroca *et al.*, 2015; Jurado-Flores *et al.*, 2021). Different studies on this posttranslational modification of specific proteins have shown that this modification results in changes to the function of the proteins, altering their catalytic activity or intracellular location and inducing important physiological effects ranging from regulation of autophagy, ABA-dependent stomatal closure, ethylene biosynthesis and root hair growth to resistance to oxidative stress (Table 1). Persulfides on specific Cys residues have been described in different Arabidopsis proteins, including abscisic acid insensitive 4 (ABI4) (Zhou *et al.*, 2021a), cytosolic ascorbate peroxidase 1 (APX1) (Aroca *et al.*, 2015), cytosolic glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GapC1) (Aroca *et al.*, 2017b), actin 2 (ACT2) (Li *et al.*, 2018), L-cysteine desulfhydrase (DES1), respiratory burst oxidase homolog protein D (RBOHD) (Shen *et al.*, 2020), SNF1-related protein kinase SnRK2.6 (Chen *et al.*, 2020) and the autophagic proteins ATG4a and ATG18a (Aroca *et al.*, 2021a; Laureano-Marin *et al.*, 2020). In addition, tomato 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid oxidases 1 and 2 (LeACO1 and LeACO2, respectively) (Jia *et al.*, 2018) and tomato antioxidant enzymes (Li *et al.*, 2020) have also been demonstrated to be persulfidated on specific Cys residues (Table 1).

Numerous biochemical and genetic data have undoubtedly established the signaling effect of H₂S in cells through persulfidation, with important consequences for numerous physiological and pathological processes in mammals and plants (Aroca *et al.*, 2020; Paul and Snyder, 2018; Yuan *et al.*, 2017). However, the precise mechanism that leads to the modification and the sulfur species that produces the protein persulfide formation is the subject of extensive debate and study. H₂S, or its ionic forms, HS⁻ and S²⁻, cannot react directly with protein thiols and requires the presence of an oxidant. Thus, H₂S can react with oxidized cysteine residues as sulfenic acid (R-SOH), but also with protein nitrosothiols (R-SNO) to give protein persulfides, but this latter process is thermodynamically unfavorable (Filipovic *et al.*, 2012). H₂S can also chemically react with disulfides (R-S-S-R) but seems unlikely due to the low level of intracellular H₂S and the slow reaction rate (Filipovic, 2015). Therefore, the reaction of H₂S with protein sulfenic acid to form protein persulfide seems the most plausible explanation for H₂S action. Cysteine residue oxidation represents a way for redox control of protein function; and therefore, H₂O₂ signaling takes place via the oxidation of cysteine to sulfenic acid, and the direct outcome of proteins is protein sulfenylation (Cuevasanta *et al.*, 2015; Willems *et al.*, 2020; Zivanovic *et al.*, 2019). Although sulfenylated residues (R-SOH) can be reversed to reduced thiol by the action of a diverse set of reducing enzymes, stress conditions can lead to the

overoxidation of cysteine residues originating the sulfinic (-SO₂H) or sulfonic (-SO₃H) motifs that are irreversible (Zaffagnini *et al.*, 2019). However, in the catalytic cycle of peroxiredoxins it was shown that the sulfinic Cys can be reduced by sulfiredoxin in the presence of ATP via the formation of a phosphoryl intermediate (Sevilla *et al.*, 2015). Protein sulfenic acid residues can react either with low molecular weight (LMW) thiols or with H₂S (HS⁻ ionic form) but the later shows significant higher rate constant (Fig. 1). In fact, protein sulfenic residues react two orders of magnitude faster with H₂S than with glutathione (Cuevasanta *et al.*, 2015). Since H₂S reacts with sulfenylated residues to form persulfide, protein persulfidation may play a role in H₂O₂-based signal transduction by preventing the overoxidation of cysteine residues, resulting in the loss of protein function. Under persistent oxidation stress, persulfidated proteins can react with ROS to form perthiosulfenic acids (-SSOH), and in the presence of excess oxidant, perthiosulfenic acid can be oxidized to perthiosulfinic (-SSO₂H) and perthiosulfonic acid (-SSO₃H) (Aroca *et al.*, 2018; Filipovic *et al.*, 2018). These oxidized perthiol residues can be reduced back to thiol by the action of glutathione and thioredoxin systems, as has been demonstrated in mouse liver (Doka *et al.*, 2020; Zivanovic *et al.*, 2019). The protective effect of persulfidation against overoxidation has also been shown in different cell types, where protein persulfidation increases following a phase-shifted curve after an increase in protein sulfenylation (Zivanovic *et al.*, 2019) (Fig. 1).

Redox regulation has been shown to be involved in many signaling processes that regulate environmental (biotic and abiotic) stress responses (Alvarez *et al.*, 2012; Hancock, 2019), development (Deng *et al.*, 2020; Jia *et al.*, 2015) or autophagy and cell death (Gotor *et al.*, 2013; Perez-Perez *et al.*, 2014; Xie *et al.*, 2014) processes where H₂S is also involved. There is much evidence that there is an overlap between ROS and H₂S; therefore, together, protein cysteine oxidation and persulfidation may represent a mechanism for the modulation of signaling processes induced by developmental or environmental stress events. In recent years, many proteins have been described as sulfenylation targets in Arabidopsis in several works, revealing more than 2000 targets for this modification (De Smet *et al.*, 2019; Huang *et al.*, 2019; Wei *et al.*, 2020). A comparison performed between the sulfenylated and the previously identified persulfidated proteins, more than 6000 targets (Aroca *et al.*, 2017a; Aroca *et al.*, 2015; Jurado-Flores *et al.*, 2021; Laureano-Marin *et al.*, 2020) revealed that 82% of the sulfenylated proteome described in Arabidopsis also undergoes persulfidation (Fig. 2A). A total of 1701 proteins are targets for either sulfenylation or persulfidation, a number that must be underestimated taking into account that the Arabidopsis samples were very different in all these proteomic analyses. Despite the probable differences in their metabolism, the number of common proteins in both proteomes is considerably high, revealing the role of these modifications in the finely tuned balance between H₂O₂-based signal transduction and protection against overoxidation. Gene ontology (GO) enrichment analysis of these proteins showed that several of these targets are associated with abiotic stress response-related GO terms, such as response to

cadmium (170), metal ion (180) and zinc (12), response to oxidative stress (61) and cellular response to oxidative stress (17), response to cold (57), response to heat (51), response to reactive oxygen species (24) and hydrogen peroxide (11), among others (Fig. 2B). Included in these targets, three L-ascorbate peroxidases, four dehydroascorbate reductases, three glutaredoxins, ten thioredoxins, two nitrate reductases, and numerous FAD/NAD(P)-oxidoreductases were found to be regulated by persulfidation and sulfenylation (Table S1 at Zenodo; 10.5281/zenodo.4727057; (Aroca *et al.*, 2021b), underlying the signaling role of these modifications in the activation of the antioxidant system against oxidative stress. Besides, GO enrichment showed that among those proteins regulated by persulfidation and sulfenylation they were found targets involved in response to biotic stress, hormones, signaling, other posttranslational modifications and transport (Fig. 2B).

Role of hydrogen sulfide in ABA signaling

In plants, precise mechanisms have been developed to perceive environmental stress. ABA, an important plant hormone, is involved in the regulation of growth and developmental processes and defense against various environmental stresses. ABA is a central regulator that triggers complex signaling networks and is also involved in stomatal movement. Under certain conditions, ABA concentrations increase to activate these signaling pathways, and consequently, ABA binds to the ABA receptor protein family members Pyrabactin Resistance 1 (PYR1)/ PYR1-Like (PYL)/ Regulatory Component of ABA receptor (RCAR), and inhibits the activity of clade A protein phosphatases (PP2Cs) (Fujii *et al.*, 2009; Ma *et al.*, 2009; Park *et al.*, 2009). This process then results in the release of sucrose nonfermenting 1 (SNF1)-related protein kinase 2s (SnRK2s) from suppression by the PP2Cs, enabling the activation of SnRK2 protein kinases. These kinases subsequently phosphorylate and activate dozens of downstream targets (Hauser *et al.*, 2017).

Extensive and convincing evidence published in the last decade has shown a close interrelation between H₂S and physiological processes regulated by the hormone ABA, suggesting crosstalk occurs between both molecules in regulation and signaling in plants (Aroca *et al.*, 2020; Gotor *et al.*, 2019). It has been widely reported that H₂S plays a role in stomatal closure, and the latest data are discussed in detail below. In addition to its role in plant growth and development, ABA plays a crucial role in plant responses to environmental stresses such as drought, salinity, osmotic stress and heat stress, processes in which H₂S has shown a protective effect alleviating the oxidative stress associated with these adverse conditions (Gotor *et al.*, 2019). There is a large amount of additional evidence that

interconnects H₂S signaling with other plant processes regulated by ABA beyond mere antioxidant defenses. For example, it has been observed that the response to drought or heat mediated by ABA induces the accumulation of intracellular H₂S, and exogenous H₂S addition increases plant tolerance to these stresses (Jin *et al.*, 2011; Li and Jin, 2016). It has also been observed that ABA shows an opposite effect on the transcriptional regulation of the cytosolic L-cysteine desulphydrase (DES1) that catalyzes the desulfuration of cysteine to generate H₂S, depending on the tissue, inhibiting its transcription in mesophyll cells and increasing its transcription in guard cell-enriched tissues (Scuffi *et al.*, 2014). In general, sulfate availability affects the ABA content and germination response to ABA and salt stress, highlighting the importance of sulfur for stress tolerance (Cao *et al.*, 2014). From a molecular point of view, the most extensive proteomic analysis published to date on protein persulfidation has shown that several proteins involved in ABA signaling, such as the pyrabactin resistance receptor 1 (PYR1) and pyrabactin resistance-like receptor (PYL), SnRK2.2 protein kinase, and protein phosphatase HAB2, are capable of being persulfidated (Aroca *et al.*, 2017a).

Recently, a publication about ABA-triggered persulfidation of proteins (Laureano-Marin *et al.*, 2020) revealed nearly 800 proteins that undergo persulfidation in response to ABA treatment in comparison with an untreated control (Table S2 at Zenodo). Data can be obtained from ProteomeXchange Consortium via PRIDE (Vizcaíno *et al.*, 2016) partner repository with the identifier PXD019802. The GO enrichment data of the persulfidated proteins induced by ABA treatment were processed using AgriGO, (Table S3 at Zenodo). The GO term associated with response to stimulus, which contained 778 proteins, was analyzed to identify the most enriched GO terms (Fig. 3A), and it included 23 proteins in response to osmotic stress, 32 in response to temperature stimulus, 19 in response to oxidative stress, 24 in response to cold, 22 in response to salt stress and 13 in response to water deprivation. Besides, other 52, 19 and 36 proteins were involved in defense response, wounding and biotic stimulus, respectively. All the ABA-induced persulfidated proteins involved in abiotic stress are listed in Table S4 at Zenodo.

Overall, these results show that ABA treatment triggers persulfidation of a high number of proteins, and some of them aim to activate a cellular response to combat abiotic and biotic stresses. In addition, a total of 276 of these abscisic acid-induced persulfidated proteins have been described as being sulfenylated. Further analysis of these targets shows that there are proteins involved in the response to abiotic stresses that are also susceptible to persulfidation and sulfenylation. The GO enrichment data of the persulfidated proteins induced by ABA treatment, which can be also targets for sulfenylation were processed using AgriGo tool (Table S5 at Zenodo), and a selection of the GO enriched terms associated with the stress response was constructed to identify the most enriched GO terms (Fig. 3B). Those GO terms more represented were response to endoplasmic reticulum stress (GO:0034976) with a p-value of 0.000042 and a FDR of 0.00076, including 6 proteins in this GO term; response to cadmium (GO:0046686) with scores of $4.2 \cdot 10^{-16}$ and $8.8 \cdot 10^{-14}$ of p-value and FDR,

respectively; and response to heat (GO:0009408) and cold (GO:0009409) with p-values of 0.00094 and 0.0017, and FDR of 0.012 and 0.02, respectively. Nevertheless, as shown in Figure 3B, other important GO terms, such as response to osmotic stress, signal transduction and response to hormone are overrepresented. These results highlight the existence of crosstalk between sulfenylation and persulfidation in response to certain abiotic stresses and that protein posttranslational modifications play an important role in regulating these responses.

Role of hydrogen sulfide in guard cell ABA signaling

As pointed out previously, the activation of ABA signaling pathways induces downstream targets that, in conjunction with ROS, Ca²⁺ and Ca²⁺-dependent protein kinases (CDPKs), activate ion channels to mediate stomatal closure and reduce water loss from transpiration (Mustilli *et al.*, 2002; Papanatsiou *et al.*, 2015). The participation of H₂S in stomatal closure has also been described previously (Garcia-Mata and Lamattina, 2010; Jin *et al.*, 2013). An initial study showed that ABA cannot induce the stomatal closure of *des* knockout mutants deficient in cytosolic DES1, which produces H₂S in the cytosol (Alvarez *et al.*, 2010), while the addition of an exogenous H₂S donor restored the closure. Moreover, ABA-dependent stomatal closure was partially blocked by an inhibitor of L-cysteine desulhydrase and a scavenger of H₂S, DL-propargylglycine (PAG) and hypotaurine (HT), respectively, suggesting that H₂S participates in ABA-triggered stomatal movement (Scuffi *et al.*, 2014). Although DES1 is expressed at all growth stages, at the tissue level, GFP expression driven by the *DES1* promoter is very high in guard cells (Laureano-Marín *et al.*, 2014). It is also noteworthy that *DES1* gene expression level in the RNA extracts of epidermal cells was several-fold higher than that in the mesophyll cell-enriched samples upon ABA treatment (Scuffi *et al.*, 2014), which provides a clue that the high expression level of *DES1* in epidermal cells may largely be due to the proportion of guard cells. Recently, genetic evidence also indicated that guard cell-specific expressed DES1 is required for *in situ* H₂S production and is sufficient in regulating ABA-induced stomatal closure (Zhang *et al.*, 2020).

The synthesis of ABA is a central response to stress. Interestingly, guard cells contain the complete suite of ABA biosynthesis pathway components. The molybdenum cofactor sulfurase ABA3 that mediated ABA synthesis in guard cells is sufficient to induce stomatal closure and relieve leaf wilting (Bauer *et al.*, 2013). Several studies have revealed that H₂S is involved in ABA synthesis. Exogenous application of NaHS was shown to increase the transcript levels of ABA biosynthesis-

related genes during PEG treatment in both wheat leaves and wheat roots (Ma *et al.*, 2016). Consistently, it was found that the transcription of genes related to ABA biosynthesis, such as the nine-cis-epoxycarotenoid dioxygenases *NCED2*, *NCED3*, and *NCED5*, sharply increased in rice seedlings under drought stress conditions, and pretreatment with NaHS further strengthened this inductive effect (Zhou *et al.*, 2020). Recently, Zhang *et al.* (2021a) demonstrated that the accumulation of all of the transcripts involved in ABA synthesis in leaves increased in wild type but not in *des1* mutants, indicating that DES1 is essential for dehydration-induced ABA synthesis. Moreover, the H₂S content was lower in *aba3* mutant than in wild type, suggesting that DES1-produced H₂S is regulated by ABA synthesis. In addition, H₂S participates in NO- and ethylene-induced stomatal closure (Hou *et al.*, 2013; Scuffi *et al.*, 2014).

Proteomic analyses have revealed that various proteins involved in ABA signaling are susceptible to persulfidation and that ABA treatments trigger the persulfidation of a considerable number of protein targets (Aroca *et al.*, 2017a; Laureano-Marin *et al.*, 2020), thus suggesting that H₂S regulates ABA signaling pathways through persulfidation of specific targets, including those within guard cells. In this way, the DES1-mediated guard cell ABA cascade is attributable to H₂S signaling through persulfidation of open stomata 1 (OST1)/SNF1-RELATED PROTEIN KINASE 2.6 (SnRK2.6) at Cys131 and Cys137, which enhances ABA signaling (Chen *et al.*, 2020). Remarkably, SnRK2.6/OST1 is also nitrosylated by NO at Cys137, leading to the inhibition of its activity and further negatively regulating guard cell ABA signaling (Wang *et al.*, 2015). Crosstalk between H₂S and NO has been previously described in the ABA signaling network in guard cells (Lisjak *et al.*, 2010; Scuffi *et al.*, 2014), and SnRK2.6/OST1 could be one of the targets driving this interplay.

DES1 itself is also activated by H₂S through autopersulfidation at Cys44 and Cys205, which leads to transient H₂S overproduction and the amplification of H₂S signals in guard cells (Shen *et al.*, 2020). Activated DES1 persulfidates NADPH oxidase RBOHD at Cys825 and Cys890 to rapidly induce a ROS burst that results in stomatal closure. Interestingly, persulfidation of both DES1 and RBOHD is redox dependent, and ROS accumulation at high levels induces persulfide-oxidation, which inhibits the activity of these proteins, leading to ABA desensitization. The oxidized persulfides can be reduced back to thiol groups by thioredoxin and prevent the continuous activation of the ABA signaling. Thus, these processes form a negative feedback loop through H₂S- and ROS- mediated modification that finely tunes guard cell redox homeostasis and ABA signaling. In addition, the accumulation of ROS induced by H₂S was also found to stimulate Ca²⁺ influx in guard cells (Wang *et al.*, 2016). Other element involved in guard cell DES-mediated ABA signaling has been recently defined, the transcription factor ABA insensitive 4 (ABI4). The DES1-dependent H₂S accumulation induced by ABA generates the persulfidation of ABI4 at Cys250, promoting the MAPKKK18 transactivation and thus, propagating the MAPK signaling cascade in response to ABA (Zhou *et al.*, 2021a). Together, these findings hint at the complexity of the H₂S signaling in stomatal movement.

The control of the stomatal closure or opening relies on the activity of ion channels and ion transport proteins in the plasma and vacuolar membranes. The regulation of inward-rectifying K⁺ channels by H₂S was shown in the sense that inactivation of the current associated with these channels induces stomatal closure by submicromolar concentrations of H₂S (Papanatsiou *et al.*, 2015). Proof was also provided by low- concentration-H₂S activation of S-type anion currents in guard cells, the process of which requires elevated free cytosolic Ca²⁺ levels and OST1 function (Wang *et al.*, 2016). All these data highlight the complexity of the relationship between H₂S and ion channels in the regulation of guard cell movement. Other secondary messengers that interact with H₂S in the guard cell signaling network have been elucidated. In addition to the above-described ROS burst produced by NADPH oxidases, phospholipase D-derived phosphatidic acid is needed (Liu *et al.*, 2021; Scuffi *et al.*, 2018).

In summary, the H₂S signaling network of stomatal movement is highly complex, and interactions among many different components of ABA-dependent signaling have been demonstrated (Pantaleo *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, accumulative evidence indicates that the H₂S molecular mechanism involves persulfidation (Fig. 4).

Conclusions and future perspectives

During past years, immense number of plant studies describing the role of H₂S in the regulation of essential processes has enabled H₂S to be consider a signaling molecule of the same significance as NO and H₂O₂. Moreover, recent reports have permitted to have a considerable insight of the molecular mechanism involved in the H₂S action in some specific processes such as the ABA-dependent stomatal closure, and importantly, to know the specific protein targets of persulfidation. Nevertheless, it is no doubt that the current challenges on the H₂S field are, in one regard, to deepen on the knowledge of the molecular mechanism involved in the H₂S action, and in the other, to ascertain what is the bona-fide sulfurating molecule that modifies the thiol group on proteins. Regarding the H₂S action, while an important effort has been made to establish chemical methods to label and enrich persulfidated proteins and technical improvement of mass spectrometers have allowed to identify an increasing number of plant proteins, mainly in Arabidopsis, the knowledge of the H₂S mechanism of action in a particular process is still scarce. As described above, insight on this mechanism has only been revealed more or less profoundly in the ABA-dependent stomatal closure

process, and in the regulation of autophagy by H₂S, although in the case of autophagy, the information is still limited.

With respect to the nature of the sulfurating species, this aspect is subjected to a great debate, even in animal systems. Due to the chemical nature of H₂S, it cannot react directly with the thiols in proteins, and several scenarios to lead to the formation of persulfidated proteins have been proposed. Thus, H₂S can react with oxidized cysteine residues such as sulfenylated or nitrosylated cysteines or disulfides, and therefore, under specific oxidative conditions the sulfurating species can be H₂S, or its ionic forms, HS⁻ and S²⁻. Other sulfurating molecules proposed have been polysulfides, which contain the form of sulfur named sulfane with the oxidation state of 0 and they have the ability to attach reversibly to other sulfur atoms (Ida *et al.*, 2014). We can hypothesize that depending on the specific condition/microenvironment of the target protein or the biological process in which the protein is involved, a particular sulfurating species or a mixture of them can be the responsible of the protein persulfidation and it would be very difficult to differentiate between them. In addition, it has been also described a prokaryotic and mammalian cysteinyl-tRNA synthetase that synthesizes persulfidated Cys for direct incorporation to proteins (Akaike *et al.*, 2017). Another interesting point is to correlate the protein persulfidation pattern/level in one specific tissue/condition with the level of the sulfurating molecules. Perhaps in the context of high level of persulfidation, it would be possible discriminate which sulfurating species is the responsible of performing persulfidation.

Data availability

<https://zenodo.org/record/4727058>

Acknowledgments

This work was supported in part by the European Regional Development Fund through the Agencia Estatal de Investigación (grant Nos. PID2019-109785GB-I00 and RED2018-102397-T); Junta de Andalucía (grant Nos. P18-RT-3154 and US-1255781); the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement (grant No. 834120 to A.A.); the National Natural Science Foundation of China (grant No. 31607255 (L458) to Y.X.); and the China Scholarship Council through the State Scholarship Fund (grant No. 201906850022 to J.Z.).

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

A.A., J.Z. and L.C.R. wrote the first draft; Y.X. reviewed the manuscript; and C.G. conceived the study and reviewed and finalized the manuscript.

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Table 1. Plant proteins persulfidated at specific cysteine residues

Protein	Accession Number	No. Cys residues	Persulfidated Cys	Effect of the modification	Reference
Arabidopsis Abscisic Acid Insensitive 4 (ABI4)	At2g40220	3	Cys250	MAPKKK18 transactivation/increase the MAPK cascade signal in response to ABA	(Zhou <i>et al.</i> , 2021a)
Arabidopsis Actin2 (ACT2)	At3g18780	4	Cys287	Inhibition of actin polymerization/depolymerization of F-actin bundles/ inhibition of root hair growth	(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Arabidopsis Cytosolic Ascorbate Peroxidase1 (APX1)	At1g07890	5	Cys32	Increase of enzyme activity	(Aroca <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
Arabidopsis Autophagy-related protein Cysteine Protease 4a (ATG4a)	At2g44140	12	Cys170	Inhibition of proteolytic activity/ repression of autophagy	(Laureano-Marin <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Arabidopsis Autophagy-related protein ATG18a	At3g62770	8	Cys103	Activation of ATG18a binding capacity to specific phospholipids/repression of autophagy	(Aroca <i>et al.</i> , 2021a)
Arabidopsis L-Cysteine Desulfhydrase1 (DES1)	At5g28030	3	Cys44 and Cys205	Increase of enzyme activity/induction of H ₂ S production/ABA-dependent stomatal closure	(Shen <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Arabidopsis Cytosolic Glyceraldehyde 3-Phosphate Dehydrogenase C1 (GapC1)	At3g04120	2	Cys160	Enhanced nuclear localization	(Aroca <i>et al.</i> , 2017b)
Arabidopsis Open Stomata1/SNF1-Related Protein Kinase2.6 (OST1/SnRK2.6)	At4g33950	6	Cys131 and Cys137	Increase of enzyme activity/enhanced interaction with ABA response factor ABF2/ ABA-dependent stomatal closure	(Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Arabidopsis NADPH Oxidase Respiratory Burst Oxidase Homolog Protein D (RBOHD)	At5g47910	10	Cys825 and Cys890	Increase of enzyme activity/induction of H ₂ O ₂ production/ABA-dependent stomatal closure	(Shen <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Tomato 1-Aminocyclopropane-1-Carboxylic Acid Oxidases 1 and 2 (ACO1 / 2)	NP_001234024/NP_001316842	4	Cys60	Inhibition of enzyme activity/repression of ethylene biosynthesis	(Jia <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Tomato Cytosolic Ascorbate Peroxidase1 (cAPX1)	NP_001234782.1	6	Cys168	Increase of enzyme activity/enhanced resistance to oxidative stress	(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Tomato Catalase1 (CAT1)	NP_001234827.1	10	Cys234	Inhibition of enzyme activity/enhanced resistance to oxidative stress	(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Tomato Peroxidase 5 (POD5)	XP_004235031.1	10	Cys46 and Cys61	Increase of enzyme activity/enhanced resistance to oxidative stress	(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2020)

Shown as the accession number, the number of cysteine residues in the amino acid sequence, the specific persulfidated cysteines and the effects and biological consequences of the posttranslational modification of the proteins. The references of the studies are below.

Figure legends

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the temporal dynamic of protein S-sulfenylation (P-SOH) and persulfidation (P-SSH) in different cell types (adapted from (Zivanovic *et al.*, 2019). After a transient ROS production induced by developmental or stress signal, the levels of S-sulfenylation in proteins are increased, accompanied by a raise in the activity of sulfide-generating enzymes and/or induction of low molecular weight (LMW) thiols, followed by a transient increase in protein persulfidation reversed by the action of reducing enzymes such as thioredoxin system (Trx/TrxR). The rate constants for the reaction of R-SOH with LMW thiols and H₂S at physiological pH 7.4 are shown (Cuevasanta *et al.*, 2015).

Fig. 2. Comparison of persulfidated and sulfenylated proteins. A) Venn diagram showing the number of proteins. B) Fold-change enrichment of GO terms of common proteins modified by sulfenylation and persulfidation. Analysis was performed with PANTHER software. The numbers beside the bars indicate the number of proteins associated with each GO term for the input set.

Fig. 3. (A) Gene Ontology enrichment of ABA-induced persulfidated proteins involved in response to stimulus. (B) GO enrichment of persulfidated targets in response to ABA susceptible to be sulfenylated. P-value for each GO term is annotated in red numbers.

Fig. 4. Graphical model of interconnections between H₂S- and ABA-signaling networks in guard cells through the persulfidation of specific proteins. Under various environmental stress conditions, in guard cells, ABA concentrations increase and trigger the DES1 activity to induce the production of H₂S to persulfidate specific protein targets. DES1 itself is persulfidated at Cys44 and Cys205, and causes the persulfidation of open stomata 1 (OST1) at Cys131 and Cys137, the NADPH oxidase RBOHD at Cys825 and Cys890, and ABI4 at Cys250. Persulfidated RBOHD produces a ROS burst that results in stomatal closure. Overaccumulation of ROS induces persulfide oxidation leading to ABA desensitivity. Persulfidated ABI4 promotes the MAPKKK18 transactivation and MAPK signaling.

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Under various environmental stress conditions, in guard cells, ABA concentrations increase and trigger the DES1 activity to induce the production of H₂S to persulfidate specific protein targets. DES1 itself is persulfidated at Cys⁴⁴ and Cys²⁰⁵, and causes the persulfidation of open stomata 1 (OST1) at Cys¹³¹ and Cys¹³⁷, the NADPH oxidase RBOHD at Cys⁸²⁵ and Cys⁸⁹⁰, and ABI4 at Cys²⁵⁰. Persulfidated RBOHD produces a ROS burst that results in stomatal closure. Overaccumulation of ROS induces persulfide oxidation leading to ABA desensitization. Persulfidated ABI4 promotes the MAPKKK18 transactivation and MAPK signaling.

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